

Workplace mental health in RN Macedonia: researcher mental health in focus

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Purpose

Workplace stress and burnout affect employees in a wide range of occupations. Health workers, for example, are exposed to psychosocial hazards that originate from the job demands and which are particularly detrimental when requirements of the work do not match the capabilities, resources or needs of the worker. Job stress among teachers has been also recognized as a common problem across different countries. According to the job demands–resources (JD/JR) model of burnout, job demands may turn into workplace stressors when the invested personal efforts are high, leading to overtaxing and emotional exhaustion. On the other hand, the lack of job resources may result in withdrawal behavior (depersonalization) and disengagement. However, according to the ReMO Researcher Mental Health and Well-being Manifesto, as well as according to the immense research literature, EU policy, and relevant institutions (WHO, ILO, EC), there is an urgent need to address mental health and well-being within academia at all levels. The purpose of the actual presentation is to demonstrate the scientific and public health efforts in RN Macedonia towards improvement of workplace mental health with a focus on researcher mental health.

Design

Relevant online resources from different stakeholders in RN Macedonia were used in order to describe the background and climate about workplace mental health and well-being, in general, and in academia in particular, and to show the current trends in research and raising awareness about this issue at the community, institutional, and policy level. In addition, official and personal contacts were used in order to obtain a thorough and comprehensive image of the policy view on mental health and mental health support in the country, as well as to describe the context of the academic system, research funding, and career advancement in academia.

Results

Relevant sources revealed that new Strategy for promotion of mental health with an Action Plan in RN Macedonia (2018-2025) has been adopted by the Ministry of Health. This Strategy has highlighted the need for adequate planning of human resources, financing of community mental health, as well as monitoring and evaluation of outlined activities. The new Law on mental health has been adopted by the Government in 2006 with some amendments adopted in 2015. This Law elaborates, among other points, the basic principles of the protection and promotion of mental health.

Ministry of Health on the official website has published recommendations for the improvement of mental health during pandemic. Official phone lines have been operated in order to help persons with mental health problems in the context of current pandemic. The National Youth Council of Macedonia recently has published a series of handbooks on youth mental health (e.g., anxiety, depression, stress) (January, 2022). It is a general perception that the mental health issue is present at the social media. The interest about the protection and promotion of mental health is increasing within the recent years. The public is particularly concerned about the influence of the societal factors on mental health. There are also increased worries about the workplace factors causing mental health problems, such as job stress and burnout. The job demands are highlighted, together with financial issues, supervisor support, and reduced possibilities for career promotion as examples of workplace factors causing stress.

The research activities of the Institute of Occupational Health of RN Macedonia, WHO CC, are strongly oriented towards evaluation of job stress, burnout, job demands, and job resources, among others, in different groups of workers. The mental health issue and the celebration of World Mental Health Day have been put into agenda of WHO Country Office in RN Macedonia. Other international organizations or their parts based in RN Macedonia (e.g., UNICEF, UNDP) have also focused their activities on mental health.

The Law on Scientific-Research Activity regulates the principles, goals, public interest, the realization of research activities, the subjects of scientific research activities and the methods of funding of those activities. This Law respects the principles of inviolability and protection of the person and dignity of man, as well as the protection of intellectual property. On the 02.12.2021, the National Council for Higher Education and Scientific Research Activity has adopted the work program for the period 2021-2025. The establishment of the National Council for Higher Education and Scientific Research Activity is regulated by the Law on

Higher Education. The National Council has been established for the purposes of ensuring, evaluating, developing and improving quality in higher education and research in RN Macedonia. One of the principles of work of the National Council is the realization of the constitutionally guaranteed autonomy that includes academic freedom, independent decision-making and management and inviolability of the University. However, the health and safety in academia (including mental health) is usually not spoken in RN Macedonia, both by key stakeholders or in social media.

Recently (March, 2022), the Chair of Occupational Medicine (within the Institute of Occupational Health of RN Macedonia) as a part of the Faculty of Medicine, Ss. Cyril and Methodius, University in Skopje, has initiated foundation of a Committee for Safety and Health at University level that would be responsible for safety and health at work of academia/scientist/researchers (both faculty members and students) at all levels of education and research. The foundation of that Committee is still in progress.

Implications

The aforementioned policy, scientific, and institutional processes that include workplace mental health have resulted in certain raise of awareness about the workplace mental health. However, the interests about the researcher mental health are still on a low level. This issue has been neglected by policy makers, occupational health and safety representatives, as well as by the working population in general. There is an urgent need to put the researcher mental health on the agenda at all levels - community, institutional, and policy level.

The efforts are taking place by highlighting this issue during the lectures of the elective subject “Job stress and burnout”, aimed at all undergraduate study programs at the Faculty of Medicine in Skopje. The issue is also included in the lectures for the students of the postgraduate Master of Public Health program. This year the training activities of the South-East European Network on Workers’ Health will be enriched with a presentation about the researcher mental health, ReMO Action and its’ Manifesto.

Resources

Faculty of Medicine. University in Skopje. <http://medf.ukim.edu.mk/en/>

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